

smFISH: tissue clearing to reduce background

Short name: smFISH-clearing

Version: 2

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Abstract: This protocol describes an approach for tissue clearing suitable for single-molecule fluorescence in situ hybridization (smFISH). Off-target binding of smFISH probes to cellular components other than RNA, such as proteins, was identified as a significant source of background (Moffitt *et al.*, 2016). Tissue clearing removes this source of background as well as autofluorescence. Samples are embedded in polyacrylamide, where RNAs are anchored to this polyacrylamide matrix, and the tissue is then cleared of cellular proteins and lipids. In this protocol, two different RNA anchoring strategies are presented, which can be used alone or in combination: anchoring by epoxide (Cui *et al.*, 2023) or a Poly-T anchor targeting the Poly-A tail (Moffitt *et al.*, 2016).

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1 Materials

1.1 Reagents

Polyacrylamide (PA) gel and clearing

1M Tris-HCl PH8	Invitrogen AM 9855G
40% 19:1acrylamide/bis-acrylamide (4% final)	A9926-100mL Sigma
Water	Invitrogen AM 9932
Ammonium persulfate	A3678-25G Sigma
TEMED	T9281-25ML Sigma
3 (Trimethoxysilyl) propyl metacrylate	M 6514 Sigma
Sigmacote	SL2 Sigma
SDS	71736 Sigma
Proteinase K	P8107 NEB
NEB3	B7003S NEB
Guanidine HCl 8M pH8,5	G 7294 Sigma
Triton X-100	T8787 Sigma
EDTA	Invitrogen AM 9260G
Coverglass	Dutscher 068764
Acetic Acid	A6283 Sigma
Ethanol 96%	159010 Supelco

Poly-T anchor

Anchoring probes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ordered from IDT at 100μM, T+ indicates T-LNA• 5'Acryd/T+TT+TT+TT+TT+TT+TT+TT-3'
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Epoxide

Glycidyl Methacrylate (GMA)	779342-100ML Sigma
NaCl 5M	AM9759 Thermofisher
Sodium bicarbonate	S5761-500G Sigma

1.2 Buffers

Ammonium solution 10%

- Prepare in water
- Aliquots can be stored at -20°C for a few weeks

Epoxide incubation buffer

- 100 mM sodium bicarbonate: adjust to pH 8.5
- 300 mM NaCl
- Can be stored sterile at RT for several months.

2 Methods

2.1 Difference from the standard protocol

- This protocol is based on the **smFISH base protocol**.
- **⚠ Here, only additional steps and changes are described.**
- **Important differences**
 - Samples are usually placed on **coverslips**; no multi-well support is used.
 - When hybridization primary probes are added, **anchoring probes** are added as well.
 - **Optional step**: incubation of the sample with epoxide.
 - Polymer **casting** (several hours) and **digestion**.

2.2 Day 0: coverslip cleaning and coating

⚠ For better attachment of the PA matrix, coverslips are cleaned and **coated with silane**.

Coating solution

Reagent	Amount
Silane 3 (Trimethoxysilyl) propyl metacrylate	3 μ L
Ethanol 95%	950 μ L
Acetic acid glacial	50 μ L

1. Coverslips are **cleaned** as described in the base protocol.
2. Prepare coating solution.
3. Coverslip **coating** for better attachment.
 - a. Let dry.
 - b. Coat coverslips with **coating solution** for 15 min (500 μ L for a 12mm coverslip in a 24 well-plate).
 - c. Rinse twice with water.
 - d. Let dry.

2.3 Day 1: Fixation and permeabilization

Performed as described in the smFISH base protocol.

2.4 Day 2: hybridization of primary and anchoring probes

- **Hybridization**: the only difference is the **addition of Poly-T anchoring probes** (if used).

2.4.1 Hybridization buffer preparation

This describes the preparation of the primary probe hybridization buffer. If used, the Poly-T anchoring probes are added during this step.

Anchoring probes dilution

- Dilute anchoring probe (100 μ M): 9 μ L SSC 2X with 1 μ L Anchoring probe

Primary and anchoring mix

- 2 μ L diluted Anchoring probe (1:10, 10 μ M)
- 1 μ L 10x NEB3 (vortex before use)
- 2 μ L primary probe
- 5 μ L Ultra-pure water

Hybridization mix

1. Heat the Hybridization buffer (see base protocol) to 90°C for 5 minutes and let it cool.
2. Add primary and anchoring mix 1: 50, e.g., 2 μ L per 100 μ L of hybridization buffer,
3. Vortex and spin down.

2.4.2 Hybridization

Perform hybridization as described in the base **protocol**.

2.5 Day 3: polymer embedding and clearing

2.5.1 Washing

1. Heat wash buffer II to 37°C in a water bath for 15 min.
2. Take the coverslips and put them in a 6/12 well-plate.
3. Wash 2X with 2 mL wash buffer II and incubate at 37°C for 30 min in the incubator.

2.5.2 [Optional] Epoxide anchoring

⚠ Handling of **undiluted GMA** needs to be done in a **fume hood** with sufficient ventilation.

1. Incubate coverslips twice in 2 mL of **epoxide buffer** for 15 min.
2. Prepared **GMA dilution in 2%** epoxide incubation buffer.
3. Add **GMA** in epoxide buffer
 - a. Cultured cells: 0.04% (w/v) GMA
 - b. Tissue samples: 0.1% (w/v) GMA (4.9 mL epoxide buffer, 100 μ L of GMA 2%).
4. Vigorous vortex after addition of GMA (solubility of GMA is about 3% in most aqueous solutions).
5. Incubate for 3h at 37C.
6. Wash **three times** with PBS.

2.5.3 Pre-incubation in PA solution

1. Prepare the first step of the **PA solution**

Reagents \ For two 40mm coverslip	2
1M Tris-HCl pH8 (60 mM final)	1.2 mL
5M NaCl (0.3 M final)	1.2 mL
40% 19:1acrylamide/bis-acrylamide (4% final)	2 mL
Distilled water	15.6 mL
Total	20 mL

2. Wash the coverslips with 2 mL of the PA solution for 5 min.
3. Supplement the PA solution with TEMED and Ammonium sulfate.

Reagents\ For two 40mm coverslip	2
10% Ammonium persulfate (0.03% final)	60 μ L
TEMED (0.15% final)	30 μ L

4. Wash the coverslips again with this supplemented PA solution for 2 min.

2.5.4 PA gel casting

1. Treat the cover glass with 2 mL Sigmacote for 5 minutes to prevent it from sticking to the gel.
2. After 5 minutes, remove the Sigmacote with a pipette and dry the cover glass.
3. Add 50 μ L of the supplemented PA solution on the cover glass and invert the coverslip onto the drop to create a thin layer of the gel.
4. Wait 1.5 h at RT.
5. After 1.5 h, separate the coverslips from the cover glass using a scalpel and tweezers, and place them in new well plates.

2.5.5 PK digestion

1. Prepare the **digestion solution** according to the number of samples you have. Two options exist: privilege delipitation (SDS) or protein degradation (Guanidine HCl).

⚠ SDS and Guanidine HCl cannot be used together, as this leads to precipitation.

Total	20 mL
Reagents	Amount
SDS 10% (2%)	4mL
20X SSC (2X SSC)	2 mL
Triton X-100 (0,5%)	0,1 mL
Distilled water	13,9mL
Total	20mL

Reagents	Amount
8M Guanidine HCl (0.8 M final)	2mL
1M Tris-HCl PH 8 (50 mM final)	1 mL
0.5M EDTA (1 mM final)	40 μ L
10% Triton X-100 (0.5% final)	1 mL
Distilled water	15,960 mL

2. Wash the coverslips twice with the digestion solution.
3. Prepare the PK solution using 100 μ L of 20 mg/ μ L PK per 10 mL digestion solution.
4. Incubate overnight in 5/2 mL of the PK solution at 37°C in the oven

2.6 Day 3: secondary probe hybridization

1. Wash samples three times with washing buffer I for 5 min RT.
2. Wash samples once with washing buffer II for 15 min at RT.
3. Perform secondary hybridization as described in the base protocol.
4. For **sample mounting**, we usually use the **liquid mounting buffer** used in autoFISH. Traditional mounting media often harden and can lead to sample shrinkage.

3 References

Cui, Y. *et al.* (2023) 'Expansion microscopy using a single anchor molecule for high-yield multiplexed imaging of proteins and RNAs', *PLOS ONE*, 18(9), p. e0291506. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0291506>.

Moffitt, J.R. *et al.* (2016) 'High-performance multiplexed fluorescence in situ hybridization in culture and tissue with matrix imprinting and clearing', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1617699113>.

4 Version history

Version	Date	Modified by	
v1	31.10.2024	Mueller F, Weber C, Laporte H	Initial version
v2	1.7.2025	Mueller F, Weber C	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.